

Dr. Trotter, on Citric Acid

Thomas Trotter

Trotter T. Dr. Trotter, on Citric Acid.

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Background

The work of James Lind, Thomas Trotter, and Sir Gilbert Blane led the British Admiralty to require that antiscorbutic treatments are administered to the ships of the British Navy [1-7]. However, at the end of the 1700s, there was poor understanding what was the cause for oranges, lemons and limes to protect against scurvy.

In this paper, Trotter was convinced that citric acid was the substance in lemons that made them effective against scurvy. The original print is at the end of this document and available through the links above.

Trotter extended the discussion about citric acid to 12 pages in his book *Medicina Nautica* [8]:

“In the spring of 1800, I observed in the newspaper an advertisement by Mr. Coxwell, chemist, of Temple Bar, for a crystallized form of lemon-juice ; and very soon after saw some of it in the possession of Mr. Kittoe, purser of his Majesty’s ship Centaur ; and which I conjectured to be prepared according to Scheele’s method. I was therefore induced to write to Mr. Coxwell, and to inform him, that if he would send me some of his salt for experiment in the cure of scurvy” (pp.391-392).

On several pages, Trotter describes beneficial effects on one patient, and stated that a few other navy surgeons found that citric acid was effective in treating scurvy patients. However, Trotter wrote the following text to the end of the chapter:

“P.S. January 31. 1802.—Since finishing this article, I have been honoured with a letter of Admiralty, inclosing me copies of a letter from the Commissioners of Sick and Hurt Board, a certificate from the surgeon of the Cumberland at Jamaica, on the inefficacy of the concrete citric acid in scurvy, and a letter from the captain of that ship confirming the surgeon’s certificate.

From the authorities given in the preceding pages of this article, I have concluded, that this preparation of the lemon preserves entire the antiscorbutic powers of the acid. I am always ready to alter my opinion when there is due reason ; but this certificate comes in a very questionable shape, and tells for nothing, as a detail of the trials does not accompany it. Mr. Watherston’s case, from the collateral evidence which appears, I maintain to be worth a thousand trials of this kind. But it is not of much importance to the subject whether the solid salt is equal to the recent fruit ; its value must rest upon curing the scurvy in any quantity however large, because it is easily portable, and may keep for ages, and cannot be adulterated without means of detection.

On the whole, I informed the Lords Commissioners of Admiralty that I continued unshaken in my opinion of the powers of the concrete acid...” (pp.401-402).

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Dr. Trotter, on Citric Acid.

To the Editors of the Medical and Physical Journal,

GEENTLEMEN,

With much pleasure I embrace the earliest opportunity to announce to the medical world, through the channel of your Journal, that I have succeeded in the cure of scurvy by the Citric Acid, in the *concrete form*, as prepared by Mr. Coxwell of Temple Bar, after the manner of Scheele.*

The history of health in the fleet for the last seven years has afforded us so large a stock of facts, that every information seems to have been obtained that could be wished, for the effectual prevention and cure of scurvy ; but there was still a *desideratum*. Some preparation of lemon juice was wanted, on a large scale, that could be preserved in every climate for the longest voyage, and that secured all the antiscorbutic virtues of this vegetable acid. Mr. Coxwell's preparation, in the form of crystals, possesses all these qualities : I also understand, that he can sell it at a price lower than the common juice, as now supplied to the King's ships; and I can vouch, that its powers against this sea disease, are equal to *any effect I have ever observed from the recent fruit in its most perfect state*.

It is highly gratifying to myself, to find that the navy and commercial part of the country are now furnished with the last article, that is necessary to preserve the lives of seamen against a disease that is inseparable from long voyages. Let me, however, remind the officer, the navigator, and merchant, that the crews of ships ought, nevertheless, to be recruited, at as short intervals as possible, with fresh meat and esculent vegetables. I should always like to see the lemon, in all its conditions, rather trusted in the cure, when we can do no better. A long use of it weakens the digestive powers, and impairs muscular action ; and thus adds another cause to the list of evils to which seamen are exposed, in bringing on that premature old age so generally among them.

It takes from sixteen to eighteen parts of water to bring Mr. Coxwell's acid to the standard of lemon juice. The gums of the patient never bled after its first administration ; they became florid on the third day ; the colour of large livid blotches on the third day, also, were evidently different in their hue, and soft to the touch : other symptoms declined in the same proportion ; and all this during the use of the ship's common fare of salt meat, &c. in order to show its efficacy in the

* Vide Crell's Journal for 1784.

Citric acid, see eg

<https://www.acs.org/molecule-of-the-week/archive/c/citric-acid.html>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Citric_acid

most forlorn state, and where the disease was well advanced. We shall, on some future occasion, detail the first cases ; where it will be observed, that we have carefully avoided those errors into which others have fallen, on holding up new remedies against scurvy.

The mind of the philosopher will naturally offer speculations on this interesting subject ; that an acid, of vegetable origin, after undergoing the process of ebullition, combination with a calcareous base, and, at last, displaced by the superior attraction of another acid, should retain the same effect on animal life, which it had in its recent form. But, *we are fearfully and wonderfully made*, and here all conjecture must stop.

The medical readers of your Journal, who are connected with the mercantile world, will naturally extend this information. In the East India service, and the Southern Whale Fishery, scurvy is a frequent disease. The concentrated state of this preparation of lemon juice, reduces the ship load to the size of a portmanteau. A besieged garrison might be relieved by dropping from a balloon a few pounds of it, when scurvy rendered it untenable, as happened with Fort St. Philip, at Minorca, last war. I am,

GENTLEMEN,
Your most obedient humble servant,

Plymouth Dock,
July 13, 1800.

T. TROTTER.

P. S. Since finishing this letter, I have been favoured with the following remark, by one of the respectable and able surgeons who has been engaged in this inquiry. He says, "I must now confess, that I have been not a little astonished at the effects of the *concrete acid*, they have far surpassed my most sanguine expectations : the proportion of an ounce of *concrete salt* of lemon to a pint of water, as used by me, tastes stronger of the *citric acid* than the common lemon juice. It is much more agreeable and palatable, being without any of that musty taste which the lemon juice always acquires."

His Majesty's Ship, Superb,
July 12, 1800.

T. WATHERSTON.

Mr. Watherston also says, that cases of scurvy, though with milder symptoms, taking the common lemon juice from the same date, continue on his list, while the others are returned to duty.

past, one theory overturning another, yet each in succession promising itself immortality. Who imagined that the doctrine of phlogiston was to be overturned so soon? — In fifty years more it may be forgotten.

But the practice of Hippocrates will endure for ever; for it is founded in truth, whose immutability neither time nor accident can control.

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